

counted. Nematode population was determined by thoroughly mixing the soil in each bucket, then taking a 250-cc soil sample for extraction using Baermann's

funnel method.

All rates of carbofuran significantly reduced nematode population. Early application of 2 kg ai/ha performed best.

For late application, 3 kg ai/ha is suggested. There was no phytotoxicity at that rate. □

Entomostracan crustaceans inhabiting rice fields

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We collected 100 samples of aquatic fauna from the rice fields in and around Ludhiana in 1982 summer, and identified species of Entomostraca. There were 2 conchostracans, 4 cladocerans, 15 ostracods, and 6 copepods (see table). □

Entomostraca from rice fields at Ludhiana, India.

Species	Order/Family
<i>Cyclestheria hislopi</i> (Barid)	Order Conchstraca Family Cyclestheriidae
<i>Caenesthereilla indica</i> (Gurney)	Family Cyzicidae
<i>Diaphanosoma sarsi</i> Richard	Order Cladocera Family Sididae
<i>Leydigia acanthocercoides</i> (Fischer)	Family Chydoridae
<i>Moina brachiata</i> (Jurine)	Family Monidae
<i>Macrothrix hirsuticornis</i> Norman and Brady	Family Macrothricidae
<i>Centrocypris bhagirathiae</i> Battish	Class Ostracoda
<i>C. madani</i> Battish	Family Cyprididae
<i>Cypris pubera</i> Muller	
<i>Cypris subglobosa</i> Sowerby	
<i>Cyprinotus cingalensis</i> Brady	
<i>Hemicypris derweshensis</i> Battish	
<i>Hemicypris malerkotlaensis</i> Battish	
<i>Hemicypris pyxidata</i> (Moniez)	
<i>Strandesia elongata</i> Hartmann	
<i>Chrissia</i> sp.	
<i>Stenocypris major</i> (Baird)	
<i>Ilyocypris biphlicata</i> (Koch)	
<i>I. bradyi</i> Sars	
<i>I. dentifera</i> Sars	
<i>I. gibba</i> (Ramdohr)	
<i>Eucyclops speratus</i> (Lilljeborg)	Class Copepoda Order Cyclopoida
<i>Mesocyclops leuckarti</i> (Claus)	
<i>M. tenuis</i> (Marsh)	
<i>Microcyclops dentatimanus</i> (Marsh)	
<i>M. varicans</i> (Sars)	
<i>Phyllodiptomus blanci</i> (Guerne and Richard)	Order Calanoida

Soil and crop management

Residual effects of straw, lime, and manganese dioxide amendments on the chemical kinetics of a flooded iron-toxic soil

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Fertilizer shortages and high fertilizer prices have encouraged research to determine the residual effect of various amendments applied to improve problem soils. To estimate the beneficial and economic effects of CaCO₃, MnO₂, and straw amendments, we need to know how long the residual effects will persist.

We conducted a greenhouse experiment to determine the residual effects of straw (2.5 g/kg soil), CaCO₃ (2.5 g/kg soil), MnO₂ (0.05 g/kg soil) amendments. Soil was collected from the top 20 cm of a Sulfaquept from Malinao, Albay, Philippines. It had pH 3.4, 0.64% organic C, 0.04% total N, 2.4% active Fe, and 0.003% active Mn²⁺. Four 3-wk-old seedlings were transplanted in each Pot in 4 replications, and the soil solution was analyzed every 2 wk.

Straw and CaCO₃ treatment depressed Eh, EC, Fe²⁺, Mn²⁺, and SO₄²⁻

Kinetics of soil solution Fe⁺⁺ as affected by the different residual treatments, IRRI.